

IMPROVING LISTENING SKILLS USING ANIMATION APPROACH IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL PUPILS

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Abstract. In this article will be discussed, explaining and teaching listening skills with modern methods, the effective ways of improving listening skills using the animation approach.

Keywords: Group activity, Video segments, Audio segments

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается процесс изучения иностранного языка, с помощью современных методов, эффективные способы улучшения навыков аудирования с использованием анимационного подхода.

Ключевые слова: Групповая активность, видеосегменты, аудиосегменты

This article examines the role of audiovisual media in the process of teaching English. The relevance of this study lies in the fact that in a secondary school, it is necessary to methodically correctly organize work based on video materials. Usage Video films open up opportunities for innovation and the use of ICT. It should be noted that video materials in modern methods of teaching foreign languages are classified depending on certain factors. A significant role in the classification of video materials is played by:

1) purpose of creation: educational and non-educational video materials are distinguished, while the main requirement for non-educational video materials is their adaptation for students; This also includes video materials shot independently or professionally;

2) genre: in this case, video materials related to various genres are offered, such as documentaries and feature films, sports reviews, news, animated cartoons, etc.;

3) the number of topics covered: this includes video fragments that cover a certain number of topics, or this topic is the only one;

4) production method: there are filmed and re-edited films;

5) didactic purpose: this includes instructive, illustrative, instructive, and illustrative fragments;

6) structure and degree of completeness: video materials are identified that represent a complete story or are divided into fragments;

7) conditions for using video materials: there are materials for students to work with a teacher, as well as independently [2, p. 17].

Video materials play different roles in teaching foreign languages.

Modern effective methods of teaching listening skills include everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening is considered to be the most learned skill. Because a little more focus on learning is enhanced through simple and fun activities and ultimately leads to better results. In this case, it doesn't matter whether you work with small or large groups of students, as long as you use one of the following methods to develop yourself. [1, p. 483-485]

Unique ways to teach students to listen well:

Interpersonal activity

Interpersonal activities are one of the most effective ways to develop strong listening skills in students. We can add the following to this method:

When developing skills and abilities in foreign language speech, video materials can act as:

- content support,
- semantic support,
- a stimulus for speech.

Videos are an important element of teaching English. The use of video when teaching listening is especially necessary. This work contains the following interpretation of listening – “this type of speech activity in which simultaneous perception and understanding of spoken speech occur.” Like any other type of speech activity, listening has its characteristics. In this regard, I. A. Zimnyaya proposes to distinguish the following groups:

1. Listening is a type of speech activity that expresses direct oral communication.
2. Listening is an active type of speech activity due to its role in the communication process.
3. Listening is a receptive type of speech activity aimed at receiving or giving information
4. Listening is a type of speech activity, the main form of which is internal. In this case we are talking about such mechanisms as listening perception, attention, recognition and recognition of certain linguistic means.

The subject of listening is someone else's thought that should be recognized.

5. Listening is a type of speech activity, the product of which is inference, and the result is the ability to understand the meaning of a statement and express a reaction to this statement. This is usually done verbally. The student will be able to react to what he heard, retain the information received in memory and use it for its intended purpose in an appropriate case [3, p. 15].

For the educational process to contain the maximum level of communicative orientation, it is necessary to use only authentic materials. Such materials can simulate any speech situation and environment thanks to audio and visual means. It is thanks to the audio and visual channels that the student will be able to receive a large amount of information during the period expected to watch the video fragment. Thanks to the visual range, it becomes possible to expand vocabulary, remember grammatical structures, and also stimulate the development of listening skills.

The use of feature films has some advantages when teaching listening comprehension since video fragments provide students with information about appearance, gestures, behavior, etc. Thus, video materials provide learners with visual support. As a result of research into the listening process, it was revealed that without the use of visual supports, it is more difficult for students to understand the meaning of a statement, even after listening to the text twice. There are two main difficulties in developing listening skills that the use of a video fragment can solve.

Firstly, work on the formation and development of listening skills involves teaching untranslatable proficiency in a foreign language. It is listening to that is the type of speech activity that is carried out based on untranslatable language proficiency. In this case, we are talking about untranslated internal speech. Since mastery of this speech can be developed at the initial stage of learning, the best way to form and develop listening skills is to develop listening mechanisms.

Secondly, it seems necessary to teach not just one person, but several, to understand foreign language speech. Thus, in overcoming the above difficulties, the use of video can significantly help. It has been proven that students can formulate their statements more fully if visual and audio

channels are used simultaneously. In this case, we can talk about more successful development of listening skills.

Thus, the need to use videos in the process of learning to listen to spoken speech should be emphasized. The following reasons are the basis of this statement. First of all, today's children experience joy when using screen media, as they are familiar with and loved by them. Secondly, when using this tool, the creative abilities of students are revealed. Thirdly, the teacher and students have ample opportunities to work on situations within a specific topic. At the same time, the teacher brings something new every time, which arouses great interest among students and increases motivation to form their statements.

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